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A new record of *Catocala lesbia lesbia* Christoph, 1887 (Lepidoptera: Erebidae) from the Republic of Azerbaijan

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ABSTRACT. The catocala moth, *Catocala lesbia lesbia* Christoph, 1887, caught in the Ordubad district of the Nakhchivan AR is recorded for the first time for Azerbaijan fauna. A single specimen was collected using UV light trap in 2018. Geographical distribution of the species is briefly discussed.

Key words: *Catocala lesbia lesbia*, Nakhchivan, Ordubad, Azerbaijan

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Introduction

Hitherto the genus *Catocala* Schrank, 1802 (underwing moths) comprises about 300 species worldwide (Goater et al., 2003; Müller et al., 2008), and 13 species have been recorded in Azerbaijan, namely *Catocala elocata* Esper, 1787, *C. nupta* Linnaeus, 1767, *C. neonympha* (Esper, 1805), *C. nymphagoga* (Esper, 1787), *C. hymenaea* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775), *C. fraxini* (Linnaeus, 1758), *C. promissa* (Denis et Schiffermüller, 1775), *C. electa* (Vieweg, 1790), *C. puerpera* (Giorna, 1791), *C. conversa* (Esper, 1783), *C. lupina* Herrich-Schäffer, [1851], *C. sponsa* (Linnaeus, 1767), and *C. deducta* Eversmann, 1843 (Aliyev, 2016; Sachkov, 2012). *Catocala lesbia lesbia* Christoph, 1887 was not previously recorded on the territory of Azerbaijan, and the fact gave us a chance to rate it as a new for the fauna of Azerbaijan.

Material and methods

In 2018, during the night collecting on the territory of the Ordubad district of the Nakhchivan AR, we caught the single specimen of *C. lesbia lesbia* using the UV light trap. All photos were taken by the first author using Canon EOS 5D Mark III. Selected locations were recorded by portable GPS eTrex Vista HCx and later adjusted via Google Earth v. 5.2. The collected specimen is deposited in the Georgian National Museum (GNM), Tbilisi, Georgia (Figs. 1, 2).

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Figure 1. A, B. Collecting site of *Catocala lesbia lesbia* in Azerbaijan.

Figure 2. Collecting place of *Catocala lesbia lesbia*. **A.** Agdere, Ordubad district, Nakhchivan AR, Azerbaijan; **B.** Village Tivi, located about 7 km SE Agdere.

Results

Catocala lesbia lesbia Christoph, 1887 (Fig. 3)

Material examined: 1♂, Azerbaijan, Nakhchivan, Ordubad, Agdere (39°6'37.67" N, 45°54'50.08" E, 1973 m a.s.l.), 2.IX.2018, leg. N. Snegovaya and I. Kerimova, GNM.

Collecting place: Agdere is located in the Ordubad district of the Nakhchivan AR. The place is a former branch of the Pulkovo Observatory, located at an altitude of about 2000 m above sea level (Figs. 1A, B, 2A, B). The vegetation cover of the area is consisted of mountain xerophytic (friganoid) mainly perennial plants. Associations are made by different species of *Acantholimon* Boiss. (1846), *Astragalus* L., 1753 and *Thymus* L., 1753, and hawthorn *Crataegus* Tourn. ex L. and rose hip *Rosa* L. dominate among the bushes (Ibrahimov et al., 2017). On the territory of the former observatory there are poplars (*Populus* sp.) planted in a row, where the development of caterpillars of this species is quite possible. In addition, at a distance of about 7 km SE this site is the village of Tivi, where there are also poplar plantings along the rivers. In addition, in gorges along small rivers where local species of stunted poplar can grow, it is also possible to find this species.

Figure 3. *Catocala lesbia lesbia*, adult male in dorsal (up) and ventral (down) views.

Discussion

Catocala lesbia Christoph, 1887 is represented by two subspecies, *C. lesbia lesbia* and *C. lesbia fittkai* Saldaitis et al., 2008 which the latter one is only reported from South Waziristan in Pakistan (Müller et al., 2008). *Catocala lesbia lesbia* was first described by Hugo Theodor Christoph in 1887 from Turkmenistan. The distribution range of this species currently includes S. Africa (Egypt, Sinai), Turkmenistan, Turkey, Iran, Afghanistan, Pakistan, and Uzbekistan (Sviridov, 2008; Müller et al., 2008; Allaberganova, 2015). Despite the fact that the Red Book of the USSR (Borodin et al., 1984) states that “the species was also found in the Araks valley in Transcaucasia”, no specific localities of collection and material is given. *Catocala lesbia lesbia* differs from the *C. lesbia fittkai* in the color scheme of the forewing, in a way that in *C. lesbia lesbia* is gray with a yellowish tone, while it is gray in *C. lesbia fittkai*. Unfortunately, our single find so far cannot say anything about the state of the population of this species in Azerbaijan, nevertheless, we hope to further study this issue in more detail. According to the article (Müller et al., 2008), this species occurs during the period from May to November. We caught our specimen in early September. Data on the altitudinal distribution of this species show that it occurs in the range from 1500 to 3750 m (Müller et al., 2008). Our specimen was caught at an altitude of about 2000 m above sea level.

Thus, it is necessary to study the distribution of this species in Azerbaijan in particular in Transcaucasia as a whole, establish control over the state of the population in this territory and develop appropriate measures for the protection of this species. This species will be studied and in further will be recommended for inclusion in the Red Book of the Republic.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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گزارش جدید *Catocala lesbia lesbia* Christoph, 1887 (Lepidoptera: Erebidae) از جمهوری آذربایجان

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چکیده: شبپره *Catocala lesbia lesbia* Christoph, 1887 از ناحیه اروباد منطقه نخجوان جمهوری آذربایجان برای اولین بار جمع‌آوری و گزارش شد. یک نمونه از این شبپره با استفاده از تله نوری ماورای بنفش در سال ۲۰۱۸ جمع‌آوری شد. انتشار جغرافیایی این گونه بطور مختصر مورد بحث قرار گرفت.

واژگان کلیدی: *Catocala lesbia lesbia*. نخجوان، اردوباد، آذربایجان